

EVALUATION OF THERMAL TRANSPORT PROPERTIES USING A MICRO-CRACKING MODEL FOR WOVEN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

This study concerns the development of a micro-cracking model for estimating thermal transport properties of composite laminates in high temperature environments. A modified shear-lag model is developed to account for the effects of thermal expansion and crack gas pressure. Local solutions from the model are presented showing the sensitivity of crack width from thermal expansion and pressure loadings.

Keywords: Micro-cracking, Thermal mechanical properties, Woven laminates

1. INTRODUCTION

Several studies have shown that the highly advantageous strength properties of many composite materials significantly degrade at even relatively low levels of heating [1-5]. In a previous study by the authors, a thermo-mechanical damage model is developed based on the use of homogenization techniques for which structure response is estimated from heating [6, 7]. This model included basic mechanisms responsible for composite damage at high temperatures including char formation, creation of gas void from resin decomposition, and thermal degradation of elasticity properties. The focus of the present effort is to improve this modelling approach by including the effects of micro-cracking that has been observed to be important for understanding early-time structure response during heating [1, 2]. To estimate the local stress distribution and the stiffness degradation due to micro-cracking, Zhang *et al.* proposed a 2-D shear-lag analysis [8-10]. In their studies, Zhang *et al.* used a local solution to estimate the degradation of mechanical properties through the calculation of an *in-situ* damage effective function (IDEF). The effects of micro-cracking on thermal transport properties, however, were not considered. In high temperature environments, the effects of gas pressure due to resin decomposition and thermal expansion have not been considered in existing micro-cracking models. Including these effects and use of the micro-cracking model to develop estimates of important thermal transport properties, such as gas permeability and bulk conductivity, is the focus of this effort. These properties are nearly impossible to determine experimentally at high temperatures and therefore detailed modeling of them is a necessity. The rest of this study starts with the estimates of thermal transport properties based on the use of a series of parallel cracks that are formed at the interface between two plies. The permeability and thermal

conductivity estimates are in terms of crack width and number density. To obtain these parameters, the micro-cracking model of Zhang *et al.* is extended to include both the effects of thermal expansion and pore level gas pressure in Section 2. Results using this analysis are presented in Section 3. Lastly conclusions from this study are summarized.

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In the current study, a composite laminate is considered composed of alternating woven and resin layers with both normal and shear loads, as shown in Fig. 1. The resin cracks are assumed to only exist in the resin layer (region 2) between woven layers (region 1) and are aligned perpendicular to the normal loading ($\bar{\sigma}_y$). The thicknesses of the resin and woven layers are assumed to be 0.2 mm and 0.4 mm , respectively. The distance between two cracks is $2s$. The initial composite material is assumed to be composed of fiber, resin and a small amount of gas void. In the resin layer with cracks, volume averages are used for estimating conductivity parallel to the cracks, and harmonic averages for estimates of conductivity perpendicular to the cracks,

$$k_x^{(2)} = k_z^{(2)} = k_r (1 - C_d W) + k_g C_d W; k_y^{(2)} = \left((1 - C_d W) / k_r + C_d W / k_g \right)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where $C_d W$ is the crack volume fraction in resin layer (C_d is the crack density, W is the crack width) and k_r is resin conductivity. The bulk thermal conductivity of both regions 1 and 2 is modeled by combining the conductivity of cracked resin and woven layers as:

$$k_x = k_x^{(2)} \frac{2h_2}{h_1 + 2h_2} + k_x^{(1)} \frac{h_1}{h_1 + 2h_2}; k_y = k_y^{(2)} \frac{2h_2}{h_1 + 2h_2} + k_y^{(1)} \frac{h_1}{h_1 + 2h_2} \quad (2)$$

$$k_z = \left(\frac{2h_2 / (h_1 + 2h_2)}{k_z^{(2)}} + \frac{h_1 / (h_1 + 2h_2)}{k_z^{(1)}} \right)^{-1}$$

where $k_r^{(1)}$ represents the conductivity of woven layer in i^{th} direction. The gas permeability induced by formation of micro-cracks is estimated as a Poiseuille's flow through the channel with rectangular cross section [11] resulting in the following relation,

$$K_x^{cr} = \frac{W^2}{12} \varphi_{cr} = \frac{W^2}{12} \left(C_d W \frac{2h_2}{h_1 + 2h_2} \right) = \frac{C_d W^3}{12} \frac{2h_2}{h_1 + 2h_2} \quad (3)$$

where crack volume fraction is used $\varphi_{cr} = C_d W 2h_2 / (h_1 + 2h_2)$. Both the crack width and crack density are required to use Eqs. (1) and (3). The focus of the following analysis is to determine the crack width using a modified shear-lag analysis with the additional complexity of thermal expansion and pore gas pressure.

Estimation of K_x^{cr} and $k_y^{(2)}$ using a shear-lag model

The shear lag model of Zhang *et al.* is modified to describe the stiffness reduction due to cracking [8, 9], with thermal expansion and gas pressure due to decomposition considered. Assuming 1) axial and shear loading on the ends of y-direction, 2) changes in the stress along the x-direction are negligible ($\partial / \partial x \approx 0$) and 3) a linear distribution of out-of-plane shear stresses σ_{xz}, σ_{yz} in the z-direction, the equilibrium equations can be integrated over the z direction resulting in the following set of simplified mechanical equilibrium conditions for region 2,

$$\frac{d\tilde{\sigma}_y}{dy} + \frac{\tau_y}{h_2} = 0; \frac{d\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}}{dy} + \frac{\tau_x}{h_2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the $\langle \cdot \rangle$ notation indicates an average value across the thickness (in z-direction) per unit width (in x-direction). The quantities τ_x and τ_y are the interface out-of-plane shear stresses at the interface between regions 1 and 2. Following the same approach as Zhang *et al.*, the distribution of shear stress through the layers is assumed to be linear. Global equilibrium relations between the average stress across the layer and the applied load are obtained by cutting the laminate vertically to expose the micro-structure stresses on the x-plane and y-plane, as shown in Fig. 2, resulting in the following,

$$h_1\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(1)} + h_2\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)} = H\bar{\sigma}_y; h_1\tilde{\sigma}_x^{(1)} + h_2\tilde{\sigma}_x^{(2)} = 0; h_1\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(1)} + h_2\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(2)} = H\bar{\sigma}_{xy} \quad (5)$$

The applied load from region 2 is transferred to region 1 (and visa versa) through the interface stresses τ_x and τ_y which are related to the deformation in each layer using a shear lag model description,

$$\tau_x = K_x(\tilde{u}^{(1)} - \tilde{u}^{(2)}); \tau_y = K_y(\tilde{v}^{(1)} - \tilde{v}^{(2)}) \quad (6)$$

where K_x, K_y are the shear lag coefficients and can be shown to equal the following,

$$K_x = \frac{3c_{55}^{(1)}c_{55}^{0(2)}}{h_2(c_{55}^{(1)} + 2\chi c_{55}^{0(2)})}; K_y = \frac{3c_{44}^{(1)}c_{44}^{0(2)}}{h_2(c_{44}^{(1)} + 2\chi c_{44}^{0(2)})} \quad (7)$$

The constants $c_{ij}^{(1)}$ and $c_{ij}^{0(2)}$ in Eq. (7) are the material stiffness matrices for regions 1 and 2, respectively, where the superscript “0” indicates the undamaged state. The quantity, $\chi = h_1/2h_2$ is the height ratio of the constraint to crack layers. Taking d/dy derivative of the equilibrium relations of Eq. (4) and the shear-lag description of Eq. (6), two independent second order linear ODEs, are derived for the normal and shear stresses.

$$\frac{d^2\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)}}{dy^2} - L_1\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)} + \left[\Omega_1\bar{\sigma}_y + (\tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)T} - \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)T}) \right] = 0; \frac{d^2\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(2)}}{dy^2} - L_2\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(2)} + \Omega_2\bar{\sigma}_{xy} = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(k)T} = (\alpha\Delta T)^{(k)}$ is the thermal strain of the k^{th} region and the constants are given in [8]. The boundary conditions for the solution to Eq. (8) are as follows,

$$\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)}(y = \pm s) = -\Delta P_g; \tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(2)}(y = \pm s) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where ΔP_g is the gauge pressure of gas in cracks. The effect of thermal expansion and gas pressure in the analysis is new and was not previously considered in the studies of Zhang *et al.* [8, 9]. The solutions to Eq. (8) are,

$$\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)} = \left\{ \frac{\left[\Omega_1\bar{\sigma}_y + (\tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)T} - \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)T}) \right]}{L_1} \right\} - \left\{ \frac{\left[\Omega_1\bar{\sigma}_y + (\tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)T} - \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)T}) \right]}{L_1} + p_g \right\} \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{L_1}y)}{\cosh(\sqrt{L_1}s)} \quad (10a)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(2)} = \frac{\Omega_2}{L_2} \left[1 - \frac{\Omega_2 \cos h(\sqrt{L_2}y)}{L_2 \cos h(\sqrt{L_2}s)} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{xy} \quad (10b)$$

where in the limit of $\Delta P_g \rightarrow 0$ the relations from Zhang *et al.* are recovered when the thermal strains are zero. The local strains for both layers can be determined using the compliance matrix and stresses as,

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)} = S_{11}^{(1)} \tilde{\sigma}_x^{(1)} + S_{12}^{(1)} \tilde{\sigma}_y^{(1)} + \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)T}; \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)} = S_{11}^{(2)} \tilde{\sigma}_x^{(2)} + S_{12}^{(2)} \tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)} + \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)T} \quad (11)$$

Using the overall equilibrium relations in Eq. (5), substituting in the local stress solutions of Eq. (6), and averaging the local strain solutions of Eq. (11) between two cracks, the average strain for each layer can be determined and are given as,

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)} = \frac{1}{2s} \int_{-s}^s \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)} dy = -\frac{1}{2\chi} (a_1 S_{12}^{(1)} + S_{22}^{(1)}) \bar{\sigma}_y^{(2)} + \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{2\chi} \right) S_{22}^{(1)} - \frac{1}{2\chi} a_1 S_{12}^{(1)} \right] \bar{\sigma}_y + \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)T} \quad (12a)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2s} \int_{-s}^s \tilde{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)} dy = (a_1 S_{12}^{(2)} + S_{22}^{(2)}) \bar{\sigma}_y^{(2)} + a_2 S_{12}^{(2)} \bar{\sigma}_y + \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)T} \quad (12b)$$

where difference between the average strains of two layers can be used to define a normalized crack width.

$$W^* \equiv \frac{W}{s} = \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)} - \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)} = -\left[\frac{1}{2\chi} (S_{12}^{(1)} a_1 + S_{22}^{(1)}) + (a_1 S_{12}^{(2)} + S_{22}^{(2)}) \right] \bar{\sigma}_y^{(2)} + \left[S_{22}^{(1)} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\chi} \right) - a_2 \frac{1}{2\chi} S_{12}^{(1)} - a_2 S_{12}^{(2)} \right] \bar{\sigma}_y + \left(\bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)T} - \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)T} \right) \quad (13)$$

With Eq. (13) defining the crack width, estimates of the bulk thermal conductivity given in Eq. (2) and gas permeability given in Eq. (3) can now be determined for a specified crack density.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 show the shear loading τ_x and τ_y on the cracked layer (region 2) for two cases of (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$. For the first case, the constrained layer (region 1) expands more than the cracked layer resulting in a tension loading in region 2 for which τ_y is negative for $y/s < 0$ and positive for $y/s > 0$. For the second case, the opposite is true, where the cracked layer now expands more than the constrained layer. For this case, the resulting shear loading on region 2 is compressive. The resulting local stress and strain distributions for the shear loadings are given in Figs. 4 and 5. For all cases, the tensile load applied to the constraining layer decreases from the ends to the mid-point because of the transfer of the load through the shear to the cracked layer. It is interesting to note that for both cases, layer 2 much more readily expands or contracts than layer 1 because of the presence of the micro-cracking. In effect, the entire load is being applied to layer 1 at the ends thereby limiting the extent for which that layer can expand or contract, however, for layer 2 the ends are free to move due to the presence of the cracks. For the case width $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$, the tension $\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(2)} / \bar{\sigma}_y$ stress of the cracked layer increases and would promote additional cracking, although the process of crack multiplication is not accounted for in the present analysis. For the case $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$, which is more typical of laminated composites where the pure resin expands more than the weave matrix, the effects of thermal expansion suppresses crack formation since the cracked layer is placed in compression.

Next, the effects of gas pressure are considered. Figures 6 & 7 present the stress and strain response of (a) the constrained layer and (b) the cracked layer for applied internal pore pressures of $\Delta P_g = 1, 2, 4 \text{ atm}$. The internal pore pressure places a compressive loading to the cracked layer which in turn is transferred to the constrained layer through the τ_y shear loading that is shown in Fig. 8. As the crack pressure increases, the

compressive τ_y shear loading increases, thereby reducing the tensile loads in both the constrained and cracked layers. If the pressure is high enough, the ends of the cracked layer are in compression while the center remains in tension.

Also, given in Figs. 3 and 8 is the in-plane shear stress τ_x which is shown to be unaffected by differential changes in thermal expansion or pore pressure resulting in no change in $\tilde{\sigma}_y / \bar{\sigma}_y$ from the baseline case, as shown in Fig. 9. The reason for this is due to the limitations of the present 1D analysis. An extension of the current analysis to multi-dimensions would be required to account for changes in τ_x from thermal expansion and pressure effects but this also adds the complexity of describing multi-dimensional micro-cracking.

From the local strains, the average strains over the constrained ($\bar{\varepsilon}^{(1)}$) and cracked ($\bar{\varepsilon}^{(2)}$) layers are computed as defined by Eq. (11). The difference between the strains is the normalized crack width, $W^* \equiv \frac{W}{s} = \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(1)} - \bar{\varepsilon}_y^{(2)}$, which is used to determine bulk thermal

transport properties. Figure 10 show the average strains from effects of thermal expansion and crack pressure. Figures 10 (a) and (b) show the strains and their difference for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$, respectively. For the first case, the overall effect of thermal expansion serves to open the crack width while for the latter case the effect of thermal expansion serves to reduce the crack width. Figure 10(c) shows the effects of pressure only result in an increase in the crack width. The pressure shown in Fig. 10(c) is normalized by the maximum pressure considered of $\Delta P_g = 4 \text{ atm}$.

At this high pressure the average strain in the cracked layer is nearly zero corresponding to a case where the entire cracked layer is in compression. Figure 11 shows the effects of both thermal expansion and gas pressure on crack width for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$, respectively. For the first case, an increase in temperature and pressure both serve to increase the crack width linearly. For the second case, the effects of gas pressure and thermal expansion have an opposing effect on the crack width. The second case is more typical of woven system where the expansion coefficient of resin is often higher than that of the weave. It is interesting to see that for some combinations of pressure and temperature the model predicts a negative crack width which is non-physical. In this case the effects of thermal expansion are sufficiently large to close the crack even at high pressures.

With the crack width determined, the crack permeability, K_x^{cr} , and effective conductivities, $k_y^{(2)}$ & $k_x^{(2)} = k_z^{(2)}$ for region 2 are computed using Eqs. (3) and (1), respectively, and are summarized in Figs. 12 through 14. The thermal conductivity of resin and woven matrix are both assumed to be $k_r = k_i^{(1)} = 0.43 \text{ W/m-K}$ and the conductivity of decomposed gas is assumed to be $k_g = 0.0338 \text{ W/m-K}$ [12]. Properties are plotted over a range of temperature and pressures and for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$. A non-linear dependence is observed for K_x^{cr} and $k_y^{(2)}$ due to their cubic and inverse dependence on W , respectively.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A modified shear-lag model is developed to account for the material damage caused by micro-cracking, and the effect of both thermal expansion and decomposed gas pressure on material damage is studied. Crack width is dependent on not only the mechanical load, but also thermal expansion and gas pressure. Using porous media relations and steady-state heat transfer solutions, relations for the crack permeability and effective conductivity are developed and explored as a function of gas pressure and temperature. Depending on the relative ratio of thermal expansion coefficients of the constrained to cracked layers, the crack width may either increase or decrease. The gas pressure, however, always results in an increase in the crack width. At high enough temperatures, the crack can close when the thermal expansion coefficient of the cracked layer is larger than the constrained layer which is expected to be the case for many laminated composites where the resin expands more than the weave matrix. For this case, gas permeability is reduced and bulk thermal conductivity increases dramatically.

Figure 1: Sketch of representative volume for woven composite system that includes interply resin micro-cracks.

Figure 2: Mechanical equilibrium of the representative volume for (a) y- and (b) x-cutting plane.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Shear loading stresses, $\tau_x / \bar{\sigma}_y$ and $\tau_y / \bar{\sigma}_y$, for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Local normalized stresses, $\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(k)} / \bar{\sigma}_y$, (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Local strains, $\tilde{\epsilon}_y^{(k)}$, (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$.

Figure 6: Local normal stresses, $\tilde{\sigma}_y^{(k)}/\bar{\sigma}_y$, for (a) layer 1 (constraint layer) and (b) layer 2 (cracked layer) for crack gas gauge pressures of $P_g = 1, 2$ and 4 atm.

Figure 7: Local normal strains, $\tilde{\epsilon}_y^{(k)}$, for (a) layer 1 (constraint layer) and (b) layer 2 (cracked layer) for crack gas gauge pressures of $P_g = 1, 2$ and 4 atm.

Figure 8: Shear loading stresses, $\tau_x/\bar{\sigma}_y$ and $\tau_y/\bar{\sigma}_y$, for crack gas gauge pressures of $P_g = 1, 2$ and 4 atm.

Figure 9: Local in-plane shear stresses, $\tilde{\sigma}_{xy}^{(k)}/\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$, for different thermal and pressure conditions.

Figure 10: Average strain, $\bar{\epsilon}_y^{(k)}$, with increasing temperature for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$ and (c) with increasing gas pressure

Figure 11: Crack width vs. gas pressure and temperature for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$.

Figure 12: Gas permeability, K_x^{cr} , vs. gas pressure and temperature for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$.

Figure 13: Thermal conductivity, $k_y^{(2)}$, vs. gas pressure and temperature for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$

Figure 14: Thermal conductivities, $k_x^{(2)}$ or $k_z^{(2)}$, vs. gas pressure and temperature for (a) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 2$ and (b) $\alpha^{(1)} / \alpha^{(2)} = 0.5$.

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